

SOCIAL SCIENCES

THE MATTER OF TRANSBOUNDARY WATERS AND LAKE BALKHASH IN KAZAKHSTAN

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Abstract

Lake Balkhash is an important landlocked water body and the second-largest lake in Central Asia, which is located in south-eastern Kazakhstan^[1]. The salient fact is that, Kazakhstan and China share waters of the Ili and Irtysh River basins, and both of them are strategic in terms of water security because in case of Lake Balkhash, the Ili River is the main water source for the lake. Moreover, the Ili-Balkhash basin's location including Lake Balkhash is the least advantageous, simply because it is downstream, whereas China has an advantage due to its position as an upstream riparian as regards access to the waters of rivers^[2]. There are numerous agreements between adjacent countries on sharing waters of transboundary rivers because of the importance of these water sources for both China and Kazakhstan. However, in spite of the fact that numerous agreements have been made, the question of water allocation is grindlocked.

Keywords: transboundary water, Lake Balkhash, the Ili-Balkhash basin, agreements, transboundary rivers, water security, water body.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the question of water allocation is gaining traction because it impacts not only economy but also ecology. Especially, in Central Asia, this matter is becoming acute on the ground of lacking agreements on water allocation between neighbouring countries and this situation worsens and threatens one of the unique lakes on the planet - Lake Balkhash. According to the research conducted by the University of Oxford, the Ili-Balkhash basin is exposed to both natural and human-made threats and in order to protect and preserve natural habitat, it is recommended to reduce water extraction for China. In detail, researchers at Oxford University carried out 738 simulations with 80 future scenarios^[3], and arrived at the conclusion that to preserve Lake Balkhash, China needs to reconsider its water use. This literature review will discover the general

situation regarding Lake Balkhash on the basis of existing researches, specifically the drivers behind retreating water of Lake Balkhash and measures that have been taken to address this issue.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The situation of the Balkhash Lake might deteriorate due to varying reasons, starting from not only losing biodiversity but also water scarcity in an arid part of Central Asia. The region has a harshly continental climate, which equally alternates between hot summers with an average temperature of around 24°C in July and cold winters with an average temperature of -8°C^[4]. Moreover, there is one interesting fact that makes this large endorheic basin unique, the west part of the lake is fresh (0.74 g/l), whereas, in the east part of the lake, water is saline (5.21 g/l)^[4] (Picture 2).

Pic.2 Lake Balkhash. Adopted from Mischke, S; Plessen, B; Zhang, C; Lake Balkhash (Kazakhstan): Recent human impacts and natural variability in the last 2900 years.

This phenomenon is explained by the fact that the Western Balkhash is fed by the inflow of the Ili River, which comprises 78% of the total river inflow^[5], while the Eastern Balkhash receives its water from smaller rivers such as Karatal, Aksu, Ayagoz, and Lepsy, constituting around 20% of the total inflow^[2]. Two parts of the lake are divided by the Saryesik Peninsula and that

is why the water composition of the two parts is different. However, this unique lake might significantly shrink due to the intensification of agriculture, aggravating climate change, and the potential basin-wide impacts of China's Belt Road Initiative, according to the recent research of the University of Oxford^[3]. Tesse de Boer *et al.* (2021) write that the Ili River is the main

contributor to irrigated agriculture in Kazakhstan and Xinjiang, although currently irrigated agriculture in the lower basin is small compared to the Chinese Ili region. “The maximal potentially irrigated land in the Chinese Ili region is estimated at 12,000 km², yet there is disagreement on the current area under irrigation (7350 to 8085 km² in 2014/2015) in the Ili Prefecture due to limited data availability and reporting” was mentioned in the article^[3].

It should be noted that before significant human impact in this region, the overall quantity of water massive of the Ili River was about 10 million tons of sediment per year, and half of them accounted for Lake Balkhash^[6]. However, due to growing cropland expansion in the northwest part of China and climate change^[7], the three main contributory rivers, such as the Kash, Kunes, and Tekes, which form the Ili River, have lost a significant part of water. On top of that, glaciers that provide water input into these above-mentioned rivers were assessed by Larissa Kogutenko *et al.* (2019) in terms of their loss, and the result of the three considered periods of time, 1962/63, 1990/93, and 2010/12, showed the loss of roughly 191.3 ± 16.8 km² of the initial area^[8]. Consequently, this situation drives changes

in ecosystems within the basin along with climate change. There is another study related to water footprint in the Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region of China, where the Kash, Kunes, and Tekes rivers are formed by snowmelt and glacial runoff, which presents the following result that the water footprint, in the region, has dramatically increased from 22.75 to 44.16 over a period of between 2006 and 2018 (Picture 3.)^[9] and the main contributors of the water footprint was blue water footprint, which is irrigation water from the surface and groundwater; green water footprint, which is the consumed rainwater; grey water footprint, which is the volume of freshwater used to assimilate a load of pollutants based on existing ambient water quality standards^[9]. Yinbo Li *et al.* (2021) discovered that “WF_{grey} is the important contributor to Xinjiang production due to the extensive use of chemical fertilizer^[1], but their data are relative scarce for Xinjiang crops; few studies estimated the difference between the actual irrigation water and WF_{blue} to measure the extent of blue water scarcity in Xianjiang; the water footprint per unit of yield (WY) received more attention to reveal water productivity from the perspective of economic benefits via the water footprint per output value (WV)”^[9].

Pic.3 Water footprint in Xinjiang during 2006-2018. Adopted from Li, Y; Deng, M; Spatiotemporal variations of agricultural water footprint and its economic benefits in Xinjiang, northwestern China.

In 2016, the percentage of total water usage for agriculture purposes in Xinjiang was around 94.4%^[10], and taking into account that fact, this region is pivotal in terms of water preservation, and this situation should be revisited from the point of sustainable water management. Back in 2001, a bilateral agreement concerning cooperation in the use and protection of transboundary rivers was signed by two sides, the Republic of Kazakhstan and the People’s Republic of China. Further, other additional sets of agreements have been signed, such as the Agreement for Emergency Notification of the parties about Natural Disasters on Transboundary Rivers (inter-ministerial); the Agreement on the Mutual Exchange of Hydrological and Hydro Chemical Information (data) of Border Gauging Stations on Major Transboundary Rivers; the Agreement on the Development of Scientific-Research Cooperation (inter-ministerial); the Agreement on Cooperation in the Construction of Joint Waterworks “Dostyk” (Khorogos River); Implementation Plan of Water Allocation Technical

Work of Transboundary Rivers; the Agreement on Cooperation on Environmental Protection; the Agreement on the Management and Operation of “Dostyk” Joint Hydro Unit on the Khorogos River^[11]; Aside from these aforementioned agreements, in 2015, consultations began on a draft of the “Agreement on Water distribution of Cross - border Rivers”^[11]. Because the main issue with all these agreements was the fact of overlooking water distribution for transboundary rivers in spite of negotiations related to this matter had been going on since 2015. According to Magzum Mirzagaliyev, the former Minister of Ecology, Geology and Natural Resources, these negotiations were tense because of China’s reluctance to include in the agreement the preservation of the ecosystem of transboundary rivers. In spite of this fact, thanks to the persistence of Kazakhstani actors, some agreements were reached in relation to the preservation of the ecosystem of transboundary rivers^[13]. These negotiations are crucial due to the deterioration of climate change in the first place. World

Bank experts — William Young, John Bryant Collier, Daniel Kull, and Jane Ebinger in their interview^[14] to the Third Pole about the impacts of climate change on water in Central Asia argued in their interview that most of the agreements related to the transboundary water had been ineffective, as an example the Aral Sea

basin. Besides, global warming, in Central Asia, is going faster compared to the global trend. There is data from The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) on the temperature changes (or fluctuations) in Central Asia^[14], and the average temperature is predicted to rise by 2-4°C in 2050 and 3-5°C in 2080 in most of the region^[15] (Table 1.)

Table 1. Climate change scenarios for Central Asia.

Country	2030	2050	2085
Kazakhstan	T + 1.4°C, P + 2%	T + 2.7°C, P + 4%	T + 4.6°C, P + 5%
Kyrgyzstan	*	*	T + 4.6°C, P + 5%
Tajikistan	T + 0.5°C, P + 2%	*	*
Turkmenistan	*	*	T + 5°C, P + 30%
Uzbekistan	T + 1°C, P + 2%	T + 2°C, P + 4%	T + 3°C, P + 4%
Mean Central Asia	T + 1°C, P + 2%	T + 2-4°C, P + 4%	T + 3-5°C, P -2%

Adopted from Zhupankhan, A; Tussupova, K; Berndtsson, R; Water in Kazakhstan, a key in Central Asian water management. T: temperature, P: precipitation, * no data.

In other words, glaciers that are the main source of water for rivers such as the Ili River and the Irtysh River might significantly shrink and this would result in water scarcity because of higher evaporation and changing rainfall patterns. As a result, water consumption would substantially be affected in the end, causing disruption of agriculture, and energy production, and lowering water availability in the long term. Moreover, I. Severson *et al.* (2016) assessed glaciers in Central Asia, and the assessment showed the pace of degradation of 0.8% a⁻¹ per year in the area, and 1% a⁻¹ per year in terms of ice^[16]. Since the beginning of the 1970s, this situation has been only deteriorating. Additionally, the situation of the Aral Sea has also contributed to accelerating the process of melting by spreading aerosols of arid origin in the upper layer of the atmosphere, which

in turn, covered the glaciers, causing the effect of heating. Those aerosols consist of anthropogenic air pollutants, mostly pesticides, fertilizers, herbicides, and salts, which are the results of the Soviet Union's agriculture policies^[17] that have been implemented over the Soviet period. This ecological disaster impacted not only glaciers in Central Asia and Lake Balkhash, but also the whole planet. For example, even the Antarctic penguins had been exposed to the Aral Sea's chemical compounds and pesticides that were later found in their bloodstream^[18]. Therefore, drawing a parallel between the process of increased retreating of mountain glaciers of the Altai, the Tian Shan, the Himalayas, the Pamirs at the beginning of the 1970s, and the desiccation of the Aral Sea between 1960 and 1987 (Picture 4.)^[19], it is clear that there is a causal relationship between these events. In other words, the global warming, environmental disaster in the Aral Sea, inefficient agricultural policies and growing water demand in neighbouring states, all the factors which add up to worsening Lake Balkhash's situation.

◻ The Aral Sea in 2000 on the left and 2014 on the right. Photograph: Atlas Photo Archive/NASA

Pic.4 The process of desiccation of the Aral Sea. Adapted from the Guardian.

In the short term, there might be some positive implications due to the melting process like rising rainfall, and as a result, the runoff would increase. Nonetheless, it should be taken into consideration that it would lead to floods, and mudflows in the low grounds, where a recipient country (Kazakhstan) is located, driving the problem of water pollution. So, this is strategic to ensure and come into agreement with China, and other neighbouring countries as to water allocation for trans-

boundary rivers in the region due to possible water scarcity in the future. The reason for these concerns is the fact that China has not signed any international agreements such as the Helsinki rules on the uses of the waters (1967), the UN Convention on the non-navigational use of international watercourses (1997), the Convention on the protection and the use of transboundary watercourses and international lakes (1992). However, M. Aujan *et al.* (2018) emphasized the fact that regardless of the agreements that had been

achieved between China and Kazakhstan, in 2007, the Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region of China released the water of the Ulken-Lasty^[20], thus, violating the Agreement of 2002, resulting in the water deprivation of the following regions Maykapchagay, Dosym and Umbetay that are located in the eastern part of Kazakhstan. As it can be seen, the matter of water has been and will be problematic for China and Kazakhstan in the light of the latest geopolitical events, increasing water demand and climate change. In the long run, Central Asia is likely to experience an increase in climate migrants because this situation lays the foundation of people having to move due to drought, floods, and shortage of fresh water.

DISCUSSION

In 2018, the first Groundswell report estimated that by 2050, climate migrants of Central Asia are expected to have reached around 2.4 million due to the aforementioned problems^[21]. There are regions that are already facing a water crisis in China, for instance, cities on the northern coast like Shanghai, Beijing, and Tianjin with a population of over 57 million^[22]. It is quite obvious that China is heading towards water scarcity. Other riparian neighbour countries, for example, Uzbekistan, also tend to unilaterally make decisions on transboundary water matters, such as building reservoirs in the Syr Darya Basin without any agreement between riparian countries that should have taken place^[15]. There is another case with Kyrgyzstan when they discharge water from the Toktogul hydropower plant in late winter and spring. By doing so, Kyrgyzstan poses a threat of flooding to Kazakhstan because discharging happens in a period of peak flows^[15]. That is why, from my point of view, it is better to address all the possible matters on transboundary rivers to avert any conflicts over water allocation going forward. For example, the way of how the matter of the Irtysh River has been handled nudges us to think that Russia and China are trying to use Kazakhstan's Achilles heel, which is a transboundary water issue, for their own gains because while Kazakhstan was trying to reach an agreement with China over the Irtysh River, Russia did not show any interest in these talks. Meaning that Russia will not probably support Kazakhstan in these questions. Basically, this question of the Irtysh River for Russia should have been important since the Irtysh River flows into the Ob River.

Poor water management is another challenge in Kazakhstan, according to the study of Nazarbayev University^[23]. Stefanos Xenarios in his interview the Nazarbayev University argues that poor water management, on the other hand, is another challenge in Kazakhstan^[23]. The use of water for agricultural purposes is assessed as inefficient and requires improvements because excessive water use should be regulated to meet commitments under the Paris Agreement and achieve sustainable development goals. In general, Kazakhstan's renewable water sources are not scarce because when it comes to the total volume of renewable water, it is estimated to be at around 6490 m³, thus, in terms of total water supply, water deprivation is not the case in Kazakhstan^[15]. However, uncontrolled water abstractions have been damaging and putting huge

stress on water over a long period of time, most notably in southern Kazakhstan. For instance, there is data on the total water abstractions, showing Pictures between 19.7-28.8 km³ over the periods of 1995 and 2010, of which 14.0 km³ was used in agriculture in 2010^[15]. This situation should be addressed by improving water-use efficiency and renovating the water infrastructure, and technologies. This is mainly the Soviet Union's legacy, leaving the country without efficient water infrastructure and institutional capacity to cope with water-related issues. Alongside, there is another issue regarding long-term plans in Kazakhstan such as maximising water extraction and lacking integration between water management and climate change. Hence, the Ministry of Ecology, Geology, and Natural Resources was created to integrate water resources management, the issues of climate change, and environmental issues. The next question is to what extent Kazhydromet's data is used by policy-makers. Because it is crucial to elevate water-related situations in accordance with data, otherwise any possible consequences will come at a high cost.

CONCLUSION

The matter of water in Central Asia has been and is a pressing matter. This situation has become uneven in the wake of the latest geopolitical shifts. Ensuring water security in the region should be addressed comprehensively, involving local water management and diplomacy channels to establish conflict mediation for settling differences between states. Turning to Lake Balkhash, China's less enthusiastic approach and procrastination to tackling the aforementioned problems on transboundary waters causes concerns not only among scientists but also among grassroots, simply because Lake Balkhash is a source of water in the arid central region and habitat for wild animals and livestock, the protection of which should preponderate across all the policies. All the actors need to keep in mind one interesting term called "the butterfly effect", in accordance with, even a small change in initial conditions begets larger consequences in the whole system to back this up it is enough to recall penguins in Antarctica with the Soviet pesticides in their blood.

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